

Bright Wetland Project, Hancock County (41.01800, -83.55700)

Since construction in 2023, the Bright Wetland Project has largely functioned as intended, with its pools capturing and retaining tile inflows and surface runoff from surrounding agricultural land. Only minor design setbacks related to outflow limit the nutrient retention of the Project.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed, with the outflow having two Agri Drain water level control structures that discharge to the Blanchard River from Pools 1 and 2. The Project has 8.5 acres of restored wetland, consisting of four wetland pools. Pools 1 and 2 receive tile inflow from up gradient agricultural fields, while Pools 3 and 4 receive surface runoff from an agricultural field on the southern border of the Project. Pool 4 overflows into Pool 3, which overflows into Pool 2. During high flows of > 1000 cubic feet per second (cfs) the adjacent Blanchard River floods the wetland. A hydrologic event at this Project defined as a storm event in which the flow of Blanchard River is > 1000 cfs and floods the wetland.

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similarly designed wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- The water control feature in Pool 1 (WCF 1) allows backflow from the Blanchard River into the pool during high flow events. Increasing the level of the stoplogs would prevent backflow into Pool 1 while increasing connectivity between Pool 1 and Existing Wetland 1 to the south, allowing nutrient retention opportunity. Raising the stoplogs would also eliminate the possibility of WCF 1 acting as an inflow during high flow events, helping to solidify researchers' understanding of Project hydrology while ensuring the Project captures water as intended.
- A low section of the walking path berm that surrounds Pool 2 has been allowing surface water to bypass the Pool 2 water control feature (WCF 2) and flow to the Blanchard River. Increasing the height of the low section of Pool 2 berm would allow water to flow through the water control feature as designed, increasing residence time within the pool. *Note:* ODNR engineers are aware of the low berm issue in Pool 2 and are making alteration plans to increase berm height.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.